

**SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN
ENUGU METROPOLIS, ENUGU STATE NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The study examined solid waste management and environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria. This study sought to determine the effect collection and transportation of solid waste on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria , ascertain the influence reuse and recycling of solid waste on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria and evaluate the effect treatment and disposal of solid waste on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population was 1994, same was used as the sample because of it small natured. Data were collected through

primary and secondary sources. Out of 333 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 320 copies (96.10 %) were returned while 13 copies (3.90%) were not returned. The hypotheses were tested using sample linear regression . The findings revealed that collection and transportation of solid waste has significant and positive effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria($B = 0.512$; $t = 9.571$; $p < 0/5$). Reuse and recycling of solid waste has a significant and positive influence on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria($B = 0.638$; $t = 14.04$; $p < 0.6$). Treatment and disposal of solid waste has a significant effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria ($B = 0.745$; $t = 11.707$; $p < 0.5$). The study concluded that Solid waste management is a growing problem around the world. The size of the problem and the lack of sustainable solutions is causing pollution, energy shortages and health problems. The study recommended that Management of ESWAMA Should use optimizing waste collection and transportation systems that will reduced greenhouse gas Emission, conservation of resources and protection of Ecosystems and promote sustainable development.

Keywords: Solid Waste Management; Environmental Sustainability; Collection and Transportation of Solid Waste; Reuse and Recycling of Solid Waste; Treatment and Disposal of Solid Waste

INTRODUCTION

Solid waste management (SWM) continues to dominate as a major societal and governance challenge, especially in urban areas overwhelmed by the high rate of population growth and garbage generation. The role of SWM in achieving sustainable development is emphasized in several international development agendas, charters, and visions. For example, sustainable SWM can help meet several United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), such as ensuring clean water and sanitation (SDG6), creating sustainable cities and inclusive communities (SDG11), mitigating climate change (SDG13), protecting life on land (SDG15), and demonstrating sustainable consumption and production patterns (SDG12) (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>, accessed on 26 September 2022). It also fosters a circular urban

economy that promotes reductions in the consumption of finite resources, materials reuse and recycling for waste elimination, pollution reduction, cost saving, and green growth

In the United States of America, before 1800s, some cities were still faced with the challenges of organized public works for street cleaning, refuse collection, water treatment, and human waste removal but it was until the early 1800s when George Waring of New York City organized solid waste management around engineering unit operations; including street sweeping, refuse collection, transportation, resource recovery and disposal (Magazzino, Mele & Schneider, 2020).

This approach was adopted nationwide, and was managed by City Departments of Sanitation. In Japan, it was until the 19th century when waste collection was private venture (Magazzino, Mele & Schneider, 2020). The government involvement was minimal and waste was treated by waste generators themselves or by private waste treatment operators. Waste was often discarded by waste treatment operators on roadsides or vacant lots and was piled up in unsanitary conditions which led to wide spread of various infectious diseases. This necessitated the enactment of The Waste Cleaning Act of 1900. The Act defined the collection and disposal of waste as the obligation of municipalities and placed waste treatment operators under the supervision of government organizations to establish a waste administration system,

The Enugu State government enacted the law that established the Enugu State Waste Management Authority (ESWAMA) in 2004. ESWAMA replaced the earlier Enugu State Environmental Protection Agency (ENSEPA) and is responsible for waste management in urban areas of Enugu State. However Enugu state government was not left out ensuring environmental sustainability through entity called the Enugu State Waste Management Authority (ESWAMA) who is dedicated to advancing responsible waste management practices across the state. As a trusted partner in fostering a cleaner and healthier environment, ESWAMA is committed to implementing innovative and sustainable waste solutions. Our aim is to create a greener future through efficient waste collection, robust recycling programs, and forward-thinking strategies.

The magnitude and diversity of the waste problem cannot be solved with a single approach. Therefore, effective waste management can be created by combining different methods. This internationally accepted approach is called "Integrated Waste Management". Integrated waste management aims for sustainability in both environmental and economic terms by addressing

waste management components holistically. In this context, waste management cannot be expected to focus on a single waste type or source. Integrated waste management takes into account that waste comes from different sources and types and includes a variety of waste management strategies (Asnani, 2006). Selecting efficient waste management strategies is key for minimizing the environmental impact and resource conservation while bringing value to the communities where they are developed. Factors that need to be considered in the decision-making process include the nature and amount of the waste to be handled, resources and technology availability, current and future policy, and environmental, societal and economic aspects. In other words, decision-makers need to take a regional approach when developing waste management strategies that will promote environmental sustainability.

Environmental sustainability stands as a fundamental tenet within the broader concept of sustainability. It asserts that meeting our needs should not endanger the environment's quality, emphasizing the necessity to preserve ecosystems for the benefit of future generations (Kaswan Choudhary, Kumar, Kaswan, & Bajya, 2019). Integrating principles of environmental sustainability into operations can augment the value of organizations and increase the significance of digitalization (Ukko Nasiri, Saunila, & Rantala, 2019). Environmental sustainability initiatives encompass various efforts to reduce environmental impact, conserve natural resources, and promote ecological balance. These initiatives, implemented by various stakeholders, including governments, businesses, non-profit organizations, and communities, demonstrate effective strategies and approaches to addressing environmental challenges. Collaborative partnerships play a crucial role, as many successful initiatives are built on collaboration among diverse stakeholders such as government agencies, businesses, N.G.O.s, local communities, and academia, leveraging collective expertise, resources, and networks to implement impactful solutions. Thus the study seek to investigate solid waste management and environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria

Statement problem

Solid waste management (SWM) is essential for environmental sustainability because ineffective practices, like open dumping and burning, cause air, water, and soil pollution, leading to climate change through greenhouse gas emissions (especially methane) and health problems. Conversely, sustainable SWM practices such as waste minimization, resource recovery (recycling), proper

disposal, and the adoption of circular economic models conserve resources, reduce pollution, mitigate climate change, and support a healthier environment for present and future generations

As urban areas like Enugu City expand, the demand for goods and services increases, resulting in more waste production. However, the waste generated is not only an environmental issue but also a social and economic one, as the inefficient management of waste can lead to public health crises, economic losses, and environmental degradation. One of the most pressing challenges in SWM is the lack of adequate infrastructure in many regions, particularly in low- and middle-density Areas . Many cities struggle with outdated or non-existent waste management systems, leading to the open dumping of waste, uncontrolled landfills, and the release of hazardous pollutants into the air, water, as well as soil. In many cases, waste management is limited to collection and disposal, with little emphasis on waste reduction, recycling, or energy recovery.

The improper disposal of waste poses serious risks to the environment and public health. Open burning of waste, common in regions lacking waste management infrastructure, releases harmful pollutants such as dioxins and furans, which are linked to respiratory illnesses, cancers, and other health problems. Leachate from poorly managed landfills can contaminate groundwater supplies, posing further risks to public health and the atmosphere. Furthermore, the breakdown of organic waste in landfills releases methane, a strong greenhouse gas that plays a major role in global warming. The environmental impacts of solid waste extend beyond local pollution. Plastics and other non-biodegradable materials that are not properly managed can find their way into rivers, lakes, and oceans, where they cause harm to marine life and disrupt ecosystems.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study focuses on solid waste management and environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria . The specific objectives were:

- i. To determine the effect collection and transportation of solid waste on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria
- ii. To ascertain the influence reuse and recycling of solid waste on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria
- iii. To evaluate the effect treatment and disposal of solid waste on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria

Review of Related Literature : Conceptual Review

Concept of solid waste

Nelson et al., (2009) defined solid waste as “Solid materials as well as some liquids in containers, which are discarded or rejected as being spent, useless, worthless, or in excess.” In another definition waste is referred to as “Lack of use or value, or useless remains. Waste is a by-product of human activity. Physically it contains the same materials as are found in useful products; it only differs from useful production by its lack of value”. (White, et al., 1999). Solid waste refers to non-liquid, non-soluble discarded materials that are no longer useful or needed. It encompasses a diverse range of materials generated by human activities, including household refuse, industrial byproducts, and debris. This category excludes liquids and gases but includes items like paper, plastics, metals, and organic waste. Effective management of solid waste is vital for mitigating environmental pollution, conserving natural resources, and minimizing adverse impacts on ecosystems, making it a key focal point in environmental sustainability and public health initiatives (Nathanson, 2023).

Collection and transportation Solid Waste

Collection and transport involves both separate or co-mingled collection of solid waste and recyclables; and the transportation to processing and disposal facilities. Collection covers the emptying of bins or/and bin bags within or around the settlement area; and transport refers to the haulage of the collected waste to the disposal facility or treatment plant (Den Boer et al., 2007). Collection is carried out in various ways in different areas in Nigeria. This includes direct collection by the state or local government or indirect collection by appointed private contractors and/or informal waste managers for a fee. The various ways include: • Kerbside collection – waste is collected from kerbs of households, where the households are responsible for bringing

out the waste to the kerbsides on or before collection days (Abdullahi et al., 2008; Imam et al., 2008; Agunwamba, 1998). • Receptacle or communal centre collection – The communal centre is usually an open space of shallow trench where waste is dumped directly on the ground or in a few cases equipped with large bins into which the waste is discharged and eventually collected (Imam et al., 2008; Dauda and Osita 2003).

Ho: Collection and transportation of solid waste has no effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria

Resource Reuse and Recycling Solid Waste

Pattnik & Reddy (2010) defined waste recycling as the organized collection, classification, and treatment of waste materials. Utilization of waste is a significant factor that has led to the possibility of recycling organic and inorganic waste fractions such as paper, aluminum, polymer, and glassware components; therefore, repurposing waste is frequently associated with the concept of recycling.

Reuse and recycling are high up in the waste hierarchy preferences and are key strategies in the circular economy. Keeping products and materials in the economy for as long as it is safe to reused/reprocessed them can extend their lives, reducing the need for extraction of virgin resource. The composition of waste in Nigeria suggests a recyclable content of over 40% despite the high decomposable fraction. Recycling rate is estimated at 8-22% of total waste with paper contributing 5- 15%, metal 10-40%, and plastics and glass 20-40% and 25-70% respectively (Wilson et al., 2009). Resource reused and recycling implemented in Nigeria is quite significant and compares well with many developed countries (Wilson et al., 2009). It is mainly carried out by the informal sector and data is generally scarce and difficult to generate (Wilson et al., 2009) as the sector is basically unregistered and unregulated and characterised with lack of planning, implementation and performance measurement and their appropriate documentation (Ogu, 2000). The waste reduction and recycling activities carried out by the informal sector includes door- to door itinerant buying of paper, metals, glass and plastics directly from source (Wilson et al., 2009) and scavenging from waste containers, communal dumps and final disposal sites. Itinerant buyers like waste pickers use waste items directly and/or sell to middle men or recycling companies (Wilson et al., 2009).

Recycling can help countries reduce pollution and GHG emissions by displacing primary raw materials. For example, a study found recycling the steel, nonferrous metal, plastic, and paper wastes components of 2186.3 Mt of solid waste over the period 2005 to 2017 in China avoided 3743.3 Mtoe (megatonne of coal equivalent) of energy and reduced CO₂ emissions by 4765.9 billion kg (Cudjoe et al., 2021). Taking the example of recycling of plastic waste, chemical recycling (specifically pyrolysis and gasification) are meant to play an important role in handling mixed plastic waste, provided that the main challenges to scale up plants for chemical recycling are overcome and, therefore, it is considered now as complementary to the existing mechanical recycling that is a relatively established process for mixed plastic waste treatment (Edo, 2024

Ho: Reuse and recycling of solid waste has no influence on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria

Solid Waste Treatment and Disposal

The waste disposal option in Nigerian cities is predominantly open dumping followed closely by open burning (Osita and Dauda, 2003). The formal treatment of waste on the disposal site is usually open burning to reduce the quantity (Imam et al., 2008). Waste collected by the private sector directly from households and evacuated from communal dumpsites is transported to final disposal sites where it is dumped in shallow pits or open grounds.

This disposal route accounts for about 50% of the total generated waste. The rest of the waste ends up in watercourses, drains, roadside spaces, underneath bridges, undeveloped properties, abandoned wells, pit latrines and borrow pits around cities (Sangodoyin, 1993; Ogu, 2000; Dauda and Osita 2003; Barton et al., 2008; Imam et al., 2008) where it is left to rot, serving as a breeding ground for flies, rats, mosquitoes and other pests. Disposal sites are generally enclosed areas with (Agunwamba, 2003) or without site officials and guards and situated on the outskirts in some of the cities such as Kaduna and Abuja and within a short distance in many others. Solid waste treatment technologies (Ma, Wang, Liu, Wang, Yang, Liu, Kong, Lin, Li,; Li, 2023) mainly include landfill, incineration and biological treatment technologies (aerobic composting and anaerobic digestion).

Ho: Treatment and disposal of solid waste has no effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria

Environmental Sustainability

Environmental sustainability refers to how the actions of individuals affect the ecosystem, subsystem, and super system upon which human beings and other organisms live (Ferdig, 2017). In an era marked by growing concerns about the environment and its sustainability, the adoption of environmental sustainability practices has emerged as a critical area of inquiry and action across various domains (Sharafizad et al., 2022). Pettinger (2018) stated that environmental sustainability concerns whether environmental resources will be protected and maintained for future generations. As the global community grapples with the challenges posed by climate change, resource depletion, and environmental degradation, understanding the evolution and impact of these sustainability practices becomes paramount. Climate change, driven by greenhouse gas emissions from human activities, is causing rising global temperatures, extreme weather events, and the displacement of communities (Ahmad et al., 2023).

Environmental sustainability practices is crucial to establish a clear understanding of what constitutes environmental sustainability practices (Khan et al., 2023; Tennakoon & Janadari, 2021). These encompass a wide range of actions, policies, and strategies aimed at mitigating environmental impact, conserving resources, and promoting sustainable development. Environmental sustainability practices can be observed in various sectors, including industry, agriculture, energy, transportation, and urban planning (Kar et al., 2022; Ozsari, 2023a, 2023b)

Conceptual Framework Solid waste Management

Researcher 2025

Theoretical Review

Empirical Review

Dilip (2024) did a study on Sustainability in Solid Waste Management to Reduce Environmental Impact and Improve Resource Efficiency. The results showed a notable reduction in waste generation, an increase in recycling rates, and improved waste segregation practices among residents and businesses. Additionally, the project successfully developed enhanced treatment and disposal infrastructure, including composting facilities and engineered landfills, which adhere to environmental safeguards. Significantly, the project incorporated waste-to-energy technologies, demonstrating their potential in reducing landfill volumes while generating valuable energy. A prototype system was developed to convert waste combustion heat into electrical energy, which was then stored in batteries for practical use, illustrating the feasibility of small-scale energy recovery from waste. Challenges encountered, such as community resistance and logistical issues, highlight the importance of continuous engagement and collaboration among stakeholders. The findings underscore the necessity of robust policies and community involvement in implementing sustainable WM practices. Overall, this research contributes to the understanding of effective solid waste management strategies and their role in achieving environmental sustainability and resource recovery, offering valuable insights for communities seeking to improve their waste management systems

Ijeoma . Ayuba, Ache . Achuen, Choji and. Musa (2014) did a study on Sustainability of Solidwaste Management In Nigerian Urban Areas: Challenges And Solution.. The aim of this paper is to examine sustainability of urban solid waste management in Nigeria, its challenges and solutions. Content analysis was employed to examine case studies in previous research, using deductive approach with qualitative data from relevant documents on urban solid wastes in Nigeria. A good proportion of the data were those compiled through observations in the course of involvement in physical planning activities, as well as teacher-student interactions in Nigeria in which the authors have been involved over the years. The results revealed uncontrolled garbage, roadsides littered with refuse, streams blocked with junks, disposal sites causing nuisance to residential areas and inappropriately disposed toxic wastes amongst others

constituting health hazards to both humans and the environment. The study recommends the adoption of environmental education and public awareness as a viable alternative for achieving sustainable solid waste management in Nigeria

Lillian and Judith (2023) did a study on the effect of effect of commercial waste management practices. Specifically, the study sought to: explore commercial solid waste management practices in Lira City, assess the level of environmental sustainability of Lira City and to examine the effect of commercial solid waste management practices on environmental sustainability of Lira City. The study employed cross sectional research design; employed both quantitative and qualitative approaches from sample size of 103 respondents that was drawn using Krejcie & Morgan (1970). The study used questionnaires and interview guide as research techniques to collect quantitative and qualitative data from primary and secondary sources. Quantitative data analysis was done using SPSS package version 23 while thematic and content analysis was employed to analyse qualitative data. The findings of the study revealed that waste compositing was the main way of managing solid waste by hotels and restaurants in Lira City. The study revealed that the level of environmental sustainability in Lira City was still below average as indicated by a Likert scale of 1-5 used by the researcher. Finally, the study indicated that the use of waste compositing and waste recycling to manage waste had a significant effect in Lira City. Based on the above findings, the study concluded that commercial solid waste in Lira City was being best managed by the use of compositing. The study therefore recommended that commercial waste management in Lira City should be managed at the local government, company, and community levels so that everybody can be in position to manage

Mesut (2024) conducted a study on Waste management and logistics play an important role in sustainability. With the increase in industrial processes and consumption habits, the amount of waste has also increased significantly. Therefore, effectively managing and transporting waste is critical to reducing environmental impacts. From a sustainability perspective, a number of strategies and practices have been developed in the field of waste management and logistics. The main purpose of these strategies is to reduce waste, encourage recycling and minimize the environmental impacts of waste disposal. Waste management and logistics can contribute to sustainability goals by reducing waste at source. With waste reduction strategies and recycling programs in production processes, the amount and harmful effects of waste can be significantly

reduced. From a logistics perspective, effectively transporting and managing waste can help reduce environmental impacts. While efficient transportation and distribution systems can reduce waste generation and carbon emissions, logistics practices that encourage recycling and reuse are also important for sustainability. As a result, waste management and logistics are critical to sustainability. Reducing, recycling and efficient transportation of waste is important in reducing environmental impacts and using resources more efficiently. Therefore, it is of great importance to adopt and implement sustainability- oriented strategies in the field of waste management and logistics

Peter, yobhebhe and Solihu (2023) aimed to determine the relationship between waste management administration and environmental sustainability in Lagos, Nigeria. Although waste production is an inevitable byproduct of human activity, sustainable refuse management remains challenging in many nations today. With this idea in mind, we conducted this investigation. According to previous research, several states lack the necessary planning and infrastructure to efficiently and sustainably manage municipal solid waste. The research population comprised 700 waste administrators in the Ikeja Local Government Area; 250 were chosen using the Yamen sample technique. However, 233 of the 250 distributed questionnaires were retrieved. In order to determine the ANOVA and coefficient results, linear regression (at a significance level of 5% or 0.05) was utilized. The results revealed a negative correlation between waste management agency operations and environmental sustainability, as well as between waste disposal, waste separation, and environmental cleanliness. Furthermore, a negative correlation between waste recycling and pollution control was discovered. Therefore, it is suggested that effective collection techniques, sufficient system coverage, proper waste disposal, institutional coordination, adequate financial resources, enforceable regulations and standards, and appropriate technology be implemented

METHOD AND MATERIALS

The study was carried out using descriptive survey design. Primary data was obtained through the use of questionnaire and observations while Secondary data were obtained through books, journals, and the internet. The population of the study was 1462 that was obtained from Enugu State Waste Management Authority. A sample size of 314 was determined from the population using Taro Yamane's sample size determination method. The instrument used for data collection

was questionnaire structured in 5 point Likert scale ranging from (SA = Strongly Agree; A = Agree ; U = Undecided ; D= Disagree and SD = Strongly Disagree) and The instrument was validated with content validity of face to face approach where managers and directors were made the necessary corrections for the instrument to measurement what it ought measure . The reliability test was done using test-retest method. The result gave a reliability coefficient of 0.92, indicating a high degree of consistency. The three hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Simple Linear Regression was used for hypotheses . A computer aided Microsoft special package for social science (SPSS) was used to aid analysis

Data Analysis and Discussion

The data obtained from the field were presented and analyzed with descriptive statistics to provide answers for the research questions while the corresponding hypotheses were tested with multiple regression at 0.05 alpha level. The five Likert scale form was design as SA = strongly agree, A= Agree, U= Undecided, D = Disagree and SD = Strongly Disagree

Table 4.1: Responses of the Respondents

s/n	Collection and transportation of solid waste and environmental sustainability	SA	A	U	D	SD	Total
1	Transportation and collection of waste minimized environmental harm	240 (75%)	51 (15.94%)	7 (2.19%)	12 (3.75%)	10 (3.13%)	320
2	The waste management industry provide employment Opportunities in area of collection and transportation of waste	270 (84.38%)	40 (12.5%)	5 (1.56%)	5 (1.56%)	4-	320
3	Effective waste waste collection and transportation reduce waste related problem such as litter, pest and odors	109 (34.06%)	185 (57.81%)	10 (3.13%)	8 (2.5%)	8 (2.5%)	320
4	Collection and transportation waste is the blood life for waste management industry to function	201 (62.81%)	98 (30.63%)	7 (2.19%)	9 (2.81%)	5 (1.56%)	320
	Reuse and recycling of solid waste and environmental sustainability						

5	Reuse and recycling reduce the demand for raw materials helping to conserve natural resource	188 (58.75%)	108 (33.75%)	8 (2.5%)	10 (3.13%)	6 (1.88%)	320
6	Reuse and recycling minimize the amount of waste sent to landfills and environmental harm	207 (64.69%)	80 (25%)	9 (2.81%)	13 (4.06%)	11 (3.44%)	320
7	The recycling requires less energy than producing new products from raw material	140 (43.75%)	150 (46.88%)	10 (3.13%)	10 (3.13%)	10 (3.13%)	320
8	The recycling of waste provides employment opportunities in collection and sorting of waste	177 (55.31%)	120 (37.5%)	9 (2.81%)	10 (3.13%)	4 (1.25%)	320
Treatment and disposal of solid waste and environmental sustainability							
9	Treatment of solid waste helps to remove pollutants and contaminants from the environment	158 (49.39%)	134 (41.88%)	6 (1.88%)	15 (4.69%)	7 (2.19%)	320
10	Effective treatment waste protect ecosystem and biodiversity by minimizing the risk of environmental harm	105 (32.81%)	190 (59.38%)	8 (2.5%)	7 (2.19%)	10 (3.13%)	320
11	Effective treatment of waste contribute to a cleaner and healthier environment by enhancing the overall quality life	111 (34.69%)	190 (59.38%)	5 (1.56%)	8 (2.5%)	6 (1.88%)	320
12	Treatment of waste and pollutants helps protect public health by reducing the risk of disease transmission	202 (63.13%)	101 (31.56%)	4 (1.25%)	8 (2.5%)	5 (1.56%)	320
Environmental sustainability							
13	Sustainable practices reduce pollution ensuring cleaner air and water for community	202 (63.13%)	100 (31.25%)	4 (1.25%)	10 (3.13%)	4 (1.25%)	320
14	Sustainable practices can reduce energy consumption by waste disposal cost	177 (55.31%)	120 (37.5%)	5 (1.56%)	13 (4.06%)	5 (1.56%)	320
15	Sustainable environment enhance the overall quality of life for the community	140 (43.75%)	23 (5.06%)	7 (2.19%)	8 (2.5%)	3 (0.94%)	320
16	Sustainable practice conserve natural resources ensuring their availability for future generation	164 (51.25%)	130 (40.63%)	9 (2.81%)	10 (3.13%)	7 (2.19%)	320

Source: Fieldwork 2025

Item 1 of table 1 Indicates that 240(75%) of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement Transportation and collection of waste minimized environmental harm. 51(15.94%) agree with the statement, 7(2.19%) were undecided, 12(3.75%) disagree that Meaningful work attracts job satisfaction while 10 (3.13%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement.

Item 2 of the table 1 states that The waste management industry provide employment opportunities in area of collection and transportation of waste 270 (84.38%) strongly agreed with the statement, 40(12.5%) agreed, 5(1.56%) were undecided, 5(1.56%) disagreed that The waste management industry provide employment opportunities in area of collection and transportation of waste non was recorded for strongly disagreed with the statement.

In item 3 of the table 1: 109 (34.06%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Effective waste waste collection and transportation reduce waste related problem such as litter, pest and odors, 185 (57.81%) agreed, 10(3.13%) were undecided, 8(2.5%) disagreed while 8(2.5%) strongly disagreed that effective waste waste collection and transportation reduce waste related problem such as litter, pest and odors

In item 4 of the table 1: 201(62.81%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Collection and transportation waste is the blood life for waste management industry to function, 98 (30.63%) agreed, 7 (2.19%) were undecided, 9(2.19%) disagreed while 5 (1.56%) strongly disagreed that Collection and transportation waste is the blood life for waste management industry to function

Item 5 of table 1 Indicates that 188(58.75%) of the respondents strongly agreed that task structuring describe how clear employee jobs are stated 108(33.75%) agreed,8(2.5%) were undecided, 10(3.13%) disagree while 6(1.88%) strongly disagreed that Task structuring describe how clear employee jobs are stated

Item 6 of the table 1 states that Reuse and recycling minimize the amount of waste sent to landfills and environmental harm. 207 (64.69%) strongly agreed with the statement, 80(25%) agreed, 9(2.81%)

were undecided, 13(4.06%) disagreed while 11 (3.44%) strongly disagreed that Reuse and recycling minimize the amount of waste sent to landfills and environmental harm

In item 7 of the table 1, 140(43.75%) of the respondents strongly agreed that The recycling requires less energy than producing new products from raw material, 150(46.88%) agreed, 10(3.13%) were undecided, 10(3.13%) disagreed while 10(3.13%) strongly disagreed that The recycling requires less energy than producing new products from raw material

In item 8 of the table 1, 177(55.31%) of the respondents strongly agreed that The recycling of waste provides employment opportunities in collection and sorting of waste, 120 (37.5%) agreed, 9(2.81%) were undecided, 10(3.13%) disagreed while 4(1.25%) strongly disagreed that The recycling of waste provides employment opportunities in collection and sorting of waste

Item 9 of table 1 Indicates that 158(49.38%) of the respondents strongly agreed Treatment of solid waste helps to remove pollutants and contaminants form the environment. 134(41.88%) agreed, 6(1.88%) were undecided, 15(4.69%) disagree while 10(3.13%) strongly disagreed that Treatment of solid waste helps to remove pollutants and contaminants form the environment

Item 10 of the table 1 states that Effective treatment waste protect ecosystem and biodiversity by minimizing the risk of environmental harm. 105 (32.81%) strongly agreed with the statement, 190(59.38%) agreed, 8(25%) were undecided, 7(2.19%) disagreed while 10 (3.13%) strongly disagreed that Effective treatment waste protect ecosystem and biodiversity by minimizing the risk of environmental harm

In item 11 of the table 1, 111(34.69%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Effective treatment of waste contribute to a cleaner and healthier environment by enhancing the overall quality life, 190(59.38%) agreed,5(1.56%) were undecided,8(2.5%) disagreed while 6(1.88%) strongly disagreed that Effective treatment of waste contribute to a cleaner and healthier environment by enhancing the overall quality life

In item 12 of the table 1, 202(63.13%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Treatment of waste and pollutants helps protect pulic health by reducing the risk of disease transmission, 100 (31.25%)

agreed, 4(1.25%) were undecided, 10(3.13%) disagreed while 4(1.25%) strongly disagreed that Treatment of waste and pollutants helps protect public health by reducing the risk of disease transmission

Item 13 of table 1 Indicates that 202(63.13%) of the respondents strongly agreed Sustainable practices reduce pollution ensuring cleaner air and water for community. 100(31.20%) agreed, 4(1.25%) were undecided, 10(3.13%) disagree while 4(1.25%) strongly disagreed that Sustainable practices reduce pollution ensuring cleaner air and water for community

Item 14 of the table 1 states that Employee commitment is achieved based on employee performance. 1775 (55.31%) strongly agreed with the statement, 120(37.5%) agreed, 5(1.56%) were undecided, 13(4.06%) disagreed while 5 (1.56%) strongly disagreed that Employee commitment is achieved based on employee performance

In item 15 of the table 1, 140(43.75%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Sustainable environment enhance the overall quality of life for the community, 162(50.63%) agreed, 7(2.19%) were undecided, 8(2.5%) disagreed while 3(0.94%) strongly disagreed that Sustainable environment enhance the overall quality of life for the community

In item 16 of the table 1, 164(51.25%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Sustainable practice conserve natural resources ensuring their availability for future generation, 130 (40.63%) agreed, 9(2.81%) were undecided, 10(3.13%) disagreed while 7(2.19%) strongly disagreed that Sustainable practice conserve natural resources ensuring their availability for future generation

Table 2 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.963 ^a	.928	.927	.23790	.287

a. Predictors: (Constant), Treatment and disposal, Collection and transportation, Reuse and recycling

b. Dependent Variable: Environmental sustainability

The multiple regression model developed shows a strong relationship between the dependent variable (: Environmental sustainability) and the set of independent variables: Waste Treatment and Disposal (WTD), Collection and Transportation Waste (CTW), and Waste Reuse and Recycling (WRR). This is evidenced by a multiple correlation coefficient (**R**) of **0.963**, indicating a strong positive linear relationship between the predicted and actual values.

The **R Square** value of **0.928** suggests that approximately **92.8%** of the variation in the dependent variable (Environmental sustainability) can be explained by the combined effect of the three predictors. This indicates that the model explains a substantial proportion of the variability, making it a good fit for the data.

Furthermore, the **Adjusted R Square**, which takes into account the number of predictors when adjusts for any potential overfitting, stands at **0.927**. This confirms that the model remains robust even after adjusting for the number of variables included.

The Standard Error of the Estimate is 0.237, reflecting the average distance between the actual data points and the model’s predicted values. A lower value here indicates that the model's predictions are fairly accurate. Hence, the regression model demonstrates a strong explanatory power and provides a reliable framework for understanding how the variables solid waste management tools (WTD, CTW, WRR) contribute to changes in the outcome being studied.

Table 3 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	229.588	3	76.529	1352.219	.000 ^b
	Residual	17.884	316	.057		
	Total	247.472	319			

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental sustainability

b. Predictors: (Constant), Treatment and disposal , Collection and transportation, Reuse and recycling

The **Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)** table evaluates whether the overall regression model is statistically significant - that is, whether the set of predictors (Waste treatment and disposal (WTD), Collection and Transportation waste (CTW), , and Waste Reuse and Recycling (WRR) as a whole reliably predicts the dependent variable (**Environmental sustainability (ES)**).

From the table, we see that the **regression sum of squares** is **229.588**, and the **residual sum of squares** (or error) is **17.884**, giving a **total sum of squares** of **247.472**. This indicates that the majority of the variation in purchase intention is explained by the regression model.

The model has 3 **degrees of freedom** for regression (corresponding to the six independent variables: (WTD, CTW, WRR) and **318 degrees of freedom** for the residual (based on a sample size of 320).

The **mean square** for the regression is **76.269**, and for the residual it is **0.57**. The **F-statistic** value is **1352.219**, which is extremely high. This indicates that the model provides a much better fit than a model with no predictors.

Most importantly, the **significance value (Sig.)** is **.000** ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the regression model is **statistically significant**. In other words, there is a very high likelihood that the relationship observed between the independent variables and Environmental sustainability is not due to chance.

Table 4 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	.040	.029		1.411	.159
	Collection and transportation	.500	.040	.512	9.571	.000
	Reuse and recycling	.641	.046	.628	14.042	.000
	Treatment and disposal	.652	.030	.745	11.707	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental sustainability

4.3.1 Hypothesis One

Ho : **Collection and transportation of solid waste has no effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria.**

- Regression coefficient (B) = 0.512
- t-value = 9.571
- p-value = 0.000

Interpretation: The result indicates a statistically significant positive relationship between Collection and transportation of solid waste at the 5% significance level.

Decision: Reject H_{01} .

Conclusion: Collection and transportation of solid waste has significant and positive effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria

4.3.2 Hypothesis Two

Ho: Reuse and recycling of solid waste has no influence on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria.

- $B = 0.638$
- $t = 14.04$
- $p = 0.000$

Interpretation: Reuse and recycling of solid waste has a significant positive effect on environmental sustainability.

Decision: Reject H_{02} .

Conclusion: Reuse and recycling of solid waste has significant and positive influence on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria

4.3.3 Hypothesis Three

Ho: Treatment and disposal of solid waste has no effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria.

- $B = 0.745$
- $t = 11.707$
- $p = 0.000$

Interpretation: Although direct marketing has a positive coefficient, the p-value slightly exceeds the 0.05 threshold, indicating that it is **not statistically significant** at the 5% level.

Decision: Do not reject H_{03} .

Conclusion: Treatment and disposal of solid waste has a significant and positive effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria.

Summary of Finding, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary Findings

The findings at the end of this study include the following:

- i. Collection and transportation of solid waste has significant and positive effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria ($B = 0.512$; $t = 9.571$; $p < 0/5$)
- ii. Reuse and recycling of solid waste has a significant and positive influence on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria ($B = 0.638$; $t = 14.04$; $p < 0.6$)
- iii. Treatment and disposal of solid waste has a significant effect on environmental sustainability in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State Nigeria ($B = 0.745$; $t = 11.707$; $p < 0.5$)

Conclusion

The study concluded that Solid waste management is one of the most important issues in sustainable development. It is important to remember that not all waste is equal, and that different types of waste have specific disposal requirements. The waste hierarchy is a framework that helps us understand this. The hierarchy starts with prevention, and moves on to reducing, recycling, and finally, disposing of waste. Solid waste management is a growing problem around the world. The size of the problem and the lack of sustainable solutions is causing pollution, energy shortages and health problems. The key to sustainable development is finding ways to reduce the amount of solid waste that is produced. This can be done by changing how people use resources, encouraging recycling and composting, or developing new technologies. Sustainable solid waste management can save municipalities money, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, improve public health, and create jobs. It can also help communities meet their legal obligations to protect water resources and improve air quality

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations were made

- i. Management of ESWAMA Should use optimizing waste collection and transportation systems that will reduced greenhouse gas Emission, conservation of resources and protection of Ecosystems and promote sustainable development.

- ii. Management of ESWAMA should adopt the strategy of reuse and recycling solid waste because it is essential for environmental sustainability, as they help conserve natural resources, reduce waste and mitigate climate change
- iii. Management of ESWAMA should treat and dispose solid waste because it will reduce pollution, prevents disease; conserves resources which promote sustainable development and at same time promote economic growth

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